

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this cetificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Ma'rupov Akmaljon Akbarovich

UY PARMALOVCHISI (ANOBIUM PERTINAX L.) NING

BIOLOGIYASI, OZIQA MANBALARI VA ZARARI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

OKTABR/ 2022

